

Deliverable 6.1

CAPACITY BUILDING FRAMEWORK

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Abbreviations

CE	Circular Economy
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
CD	Capacity Development

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Glossary

Capacity Building

The process by which individuals and organizations obtain, improve, and retain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment and other resources needed to do their jobs competently or to a greater capacity.

Circular City

A circular city is a city where the circular economy principles are implemented and result in a resilient system that facilitates new kinds of social, environmental, technological, and economic activities. Examples of which can be the strengthening of competitiveness and the generation of employment.

Circular Economy

A circular economy is an alternative to a traditional linear economy (make, use, dispose) in which we keep resources in use for as long as possible, extracting the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recovering and reusing products and materials. The circular economy concept proposes a regenerative system in which resource input and waste, emission and energy leakage are minimised by material loops. Within REFLOW, the focus of the circular economy gradually extends beyond issues related to material management and covers other aspects, such as social impact, technological aspects and the evolution of urban governance structures.

Community of Practice

A group of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly

Regenerative City

A regenerative city moves beyond sustainability, and develops a restorative, mutually beneficial relationship with the natural and social systems that sustain it. In REFLOW, the road to generative urban development will be achieved through the attention to the social, environmental, technological and economic dimensions.

Regenerative Economy

An approach in which products and services replenish their own sources of energy, water and materials in a closed-loop system.

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1. Introduction

1.1 About REFLOW

REFLOW is an EU Horizon 2020 research project running from 2019-2022, which aims to enable the transition of European cities towards circular and regenerative practices. More specifically, REFLOW uses Fab Labs and makerspaces as catalysers of systemic change in urban and peri-urban environments, which enable, visualize and regulate “four freedoms”: free movement of materials, people, (technological) knowledge and commons, in order to reduce materials consumption, maximize multifunctional use of (public) spaces and envisage regenerative practices. The project will provide the best practices to align market and government needs in order to create favourable conditions for the public and private sectors to adopt circular economy (CE) practices. REFLOW is creating new CE business models within six pilot cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris and Vejle and assesses their social, environmental, and economic impact, by enabling active citizen involvement and systemic change to re-think the current approach to material flow in cities.

1.2 REFLOW Vision

A circular and regenerative city in REFLOW represents an urban system with social and business practices which place equal attention to social, environmental and economic impact; where technology is open and represents a central enabler of positive social and environmental change; where the urban system ensures and supports resilience of social and ecological systems; where governance is collaborative and inclusive; where knowledge is shared, and stakeholders are active and involved.

1.3 About the Deliverable

The Reflow Capacity Building Strategic Framework proposed here has been prepared in accordance with the overall objectives of the Reflow project. The authors of this document aim to define the strategic direction, objectives, role and commitment of REFLOW for the period of the project and beyond.

The purpose of REFLOW Capacity building strategy is to

- Offer a repository of knowledge and best practices related to regenerative thinking at city level
- Improve relevant knowledge and support the development of local capacity and competences in pilot cities and beyond
- Offer dedicated training and education to its extended ecosystem.

At the end of the project, REFLOW positions itself as a centre of excellence for circular and regenerative practices at urban levels and acts as a facilitator and catalyst,

providing experience for practical applications and policies, and offering support on all matters relating to regenerative cities.

1.4 How does the deliverable contribute to the overarching objectives of REFLOW?

One of the key objectives of REFLOW is to facilitate and enable the transition of European cities towards a circular and regenerative economy. This transition is context and place-based and does not follow a straightforward process. Nevertheless, as described in the [REFLOW Circular City Framework](#), several levers can be activated to intervene within the boundaries of a city system. In order to enhance the capacity of city stakeholders to embrace and implement a circular mind set, Capacity Building plays a pivotal role: to inspire on what a successful transition can look like, to inform and raise awareness on the approaches that can be undertaken to successfully transition, to connect with other circular stakeholders within cities and beyond, and last but not least, to equip stakeholders with the rights tools, methods, and processes for the transformation.

This deliverable provides the ground to frame how capacity building resources should be developed within the project and in more general in CE-related initiatives at city level. The deliverable structures the activities required to improve awareness and knowledge of businesses and policy makers on the sustainable development benefits associated with circular economy.

1.5 Relation with other REFLOW Deliverables

Work package 6 in general, and this deliverable in particular, is acting as a supporting lever facilitating the implementation of actions at local level in the 6 pilot cities. When developing circular actions plans and implementing specific circular initiatives, pilots may benefit from a body of knowledge associated with already existing initiatives, best practices, reports, publications, how-to's that can support their tasks. At a conceptual level, the knowledge and insights curated within this work package are used to feed into the different deliverables produced in other work packages. At the same time, as new knowledge is generated and being extracted from the activities happening at pilot level, a feedback loop is expected in which new knowledge circles back before being redistributed. Therefore, the content of the WP 1-5 deliverables is also used as raw material to generate additional insights and knowledge to be disseminated further in specific educational formats (eLearning courses, webinars, podcasts, etc..)

Amongst all WP6 - Capacity Building and Knowledge Transfer - deliverables, this deliverable lays the ground for the development of Capacity building resources detailed in D6.3, D6.4 and D6.5.

1.6 Structure of the Report

The report is organised as follow: Chapter 2 introduces the Capacity Building theoretical underpinnings that help us frame how CB is defined and implemented within REFLOW. Chapter 3 describes the strategic approach REFLOW project is taking to implement Capacity Building; it lays out generic principles, target groups, and details a generic framework to support the implementation of the Capacity Building strategy. Chapter 4 describes the activities performed following the steps of the Framework: Competence framework development, Skills gap assessment, and Capacity Building Resources portfolio development, implementation and monitoring. The last section offers an overview of the associated deliverables in which a detailed description of the REFLOW Resources is presented.

Figure 1: Overview of the Deliverable

2. Capacity Building theoretical underpinnings

This chapter first introduces the theoretical background associated with Capacity building. It provides definitions of terms and concepts and clarifies at which level Capacity Building can be implemented.

2.1 Definition of terms and concepts

Capacity

Capacity has been described variously in the literature. It can be defined as the ability to perform tasks and produce outputs, to define and solve problems, and make informed choices (EuropeAid), the ability of an organisation to function as a resilient, strategic and autonomous entity (Kaplan, 2000); the ability of people, organisations and society as a whole to manage their affairs successfully (OECD, 2006); the ability of individuals, organisations and societies to set and achieve their own development objectives (UNDP, 2008); and the ability of a human system to perform, sustain itself and self-renew (Ubels, Acquaye-Baddoo and Fowler, 2010).

Capacity building

Similarly, capacity building can be defined as the process by which individuals and organizations obtain, improve, and retain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment and other resources needed to do their jobs competently (OECD, 2006). It is the process by which people, organizations and society systematically stimulate and develop their capability over time to achieve societal and economic goals, including through improvement of knowledge, skills, systems, and institutions – within a wider social and cultural enabling environment.

Closely associated to capacity building is capacity development (CD), the process by which people and organizations create and strengthen their capacity over time. Support to capacity development can be in the form of inputs and processes that external actors can deliver to catalyse or back capacity development of persons, organizations, or networks of organizations (EC, 2007). UNDP defines capacity development as: “the process through which individuals, organizations and societies obtain, strengthen and maintain the capabilities to set and achieve their own development objectives over time” (UNDP, 2008).

The process specifically means that individuals acquire technical and managerial expertise and performance capabilities. It also means organisations and communities acquire mainstream systems, processes and structures to become more efficient and effective, individuals and organizations perform at a greater capacity.

2.2 Different levels of implementation

Capacity building can be addressed at different levels; individual, organizational, systems levels as described in the diagram below.

Figure 2: Capacity building levels

Individual level

At the individual level, capacity building refers to the process of changing attitude and behaviour, typically through knowledge acquisition, skills exchange and training. It requires the development of conditions that allow individual participants to build and enhance knowledge and skills. It also refers to other mechanisms such as learning-by-doing, participation and the exercise of ownership.

Organizational level

At the organisational level capacity building involves strengthening performance and function. It does this by developing mandates, tools, guidelines and management information systems that facilitate and catalyse organisational change. It is also concerned with strengthening the relationship between individuals in the organisational setting and their links to their environment.

System level

At the system level (the “enabling environment”), capacity building is concerned with the overall policy, economic, regulatory and accountability frameworks within which organisations and individuals operate. Relationships and processes between organisations, both formal and informal, as well as their mandates, are also important.

Capacities at the three dimensions are interlinked: individuals, organizations and the enabling environment are parts of a whole. Capacity development often involves enhancing the knowledge and skills of individuals whose work results greatly rely on the performance of the organizations in which they work. The effectiveness of organizations is influenced by the enabling environment. Conversely, the environment is affected by organizations and the relationships between them.

3. REFLOW Capacity Building Framework

This chapter describes how Capacity building as a supporting city strategy is envisioned in the context of the REFLOW project.

3.1 REFLOW's strategic approach to Capacity Building

REFLOW brings together several stakeholders to combine their expertise in different fields relevant to the deployment of regenerative and circular practices. To be effective, REFLOW cannot become active on all levels and it cannot duplicate the work of others.

It will maximise its impact by drawing on its unique position as an innovative regenerative practice's hub and rely on its diverse partnerships to achieve its capacity building mandate.

It will pool and promote the sharing of best practices and lessons learnt and play a convening and coordinating role, aligning existing initiatives while generating new learnings.

Capacity development is driven by city actors, consistent with national priorities and the local context, and anchored in national systems and local expertise. Capacity development thus needs to be undertaken in partnership with different stakeholders at local, regional and cross-national level and requires long-term interventions rather than stand-alone short-term events.

REFLOW must determine how to focus its capacity building efforts. Pilot cities have reached different levels of sophistication as far as regenerative cities deployment is concerned. Some cities have extensive experience in developing circular initiatives, while others are just beginning their journey. They therefore, require different levels of support. These differences will be reflected as projects, experiments and new solutions in cities are being prototyped and implemented. Advanced cities will be able to support the Reflow capacity building work in other cities with less developed regenerative mind-sets. This can be achieved by sharing experiences and lessons learnt and facilitating access to expertise on specific issues.

3.2 REFLOW Capacity Building Guiding Principles

The following principles help us frame the overall REFLOW Capacity Building strategy

Systemic

Sustainable capacity building cuts across all dimensions and barriers and must take place not in isolation but across all key intervention areas. This necessitates a multi-level perspective, as illustrated in the REFLOW Circular City Framework. It means that, while tangible capacity building at all levels is important, it has to be mainstreamed into policy making. Up-to-date, attractive conditions have to be created to sustain acquired knowledge locally. A common framework to assess skills and capacity gaps is needed to give a comprehensive picture and allow for appropriate action.

Participative, inclusive and sustainable

Participation is the hallmark of all REFLOW overall approach. In order to complement existing initiatives, REFLOW capacity building framework will make the most of existing experiences, use structures and partnerships already in place and co-operate with appropriate stakeholders.

Local, regional and EU stakeholders will be involved wherever possible and wherever they strengthen and complement current efforts to ensure action is sustained. REFLOW involvement should result in structures that have built up expertise and become sources of knowledge, advice and training. Responses must be adapted to individual circumstances, given the varying needs for capacity building in different cities.

Issue-based

REFLOW acknowledges that for future capacity building programmes to be successful, its approach has to be demand-driven and tailor-made. Capacity building needs are very diverse depending on the target groups and city environments. Needs relating to specific issues will be met in order to ensure capacity building priorities are dealt with in line with cities' priorities.

Accountable

Monitoring and evaluation are critical to ensure continuous improvement of all REFLOW capacity building activities and the delivery of quality outputs. In addition, they provide a basis for proper planning, managing and documenting of activities. Monitoring will be an obligatory component of all the capacity building projects and activities Reflow intends to carry out. Targets and success indicators

must be clearly defined in order to help monitor results, evaluate progress and propose corrective measures if needed.

3.3 Target groups

CE requires multiple stakeholder networks as well as the the active involvement and negotiation of the interests of several stakeholders. Thus, the issue is at the centre of the stakeholders’ attention. REFLOW identifies multiple stakeholders who have a potential interest in the project knowledge development. These can organized into target groups which are summarized below.

Target group	Description	Interest in knowledge acquisition
A – Industry Stakeholders	Urban manufacturers and their associations as well as technology providers, in particular those operating in the domains directly related with REFLOW.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of project’s learnings in everyday operations - Training on project’ outcomes - Inspiration for new business models and application - Key knowledge requirements pertaining to transitioning to circular economy
B – Fab Labs and makerspaces	Grassroots organisations, open to the public that offer tools and services for digital manufacturing, thus promoting social and economic innovation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of project’s learnings in everyday operations - Training on project’ outcomes - Inspiration for new ideas and application
C – Public administrations	Other EU municipalities which could be interested in adopting CE practices and tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of project’s learnings in everyday operations - Training on project’ outcomes - Inspiration for new policies and application - Refinement of strategic initiatives on circular economy
D – EU Associations and Clusters	European initiatives and clusters, e.g., Covenant of Mayors, C40, Fab City Global Initiative.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dissemination of project’s knowledge to their members
E – Circular Economy Stakeholders	Participants, external partners and other relevant stakeholders active in EU projects and other initiatives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of common topics - Overcoming the technical and economic barriers to the adoption of industrial symbiosis.

F – Research & Academia	<p>Individuals engaged in research initiatives and/or working in research/academic institutes conducting research on Circular Economy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - knowledge acquisition - use of knowledge in teaching - Inspiration for future research initiatives based on the project’s concept and results - Transfer of knowledge and raising awareness - Assimilate innovative project outputs in further research and development activities
G – Policy Makers	<p>Policy makers at local, regional and national level, such as public authorities, regulatory agencies and ministries.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of project’s learnings in everyday operations - Training on project’ outcomes - Inspiration for new policies and application - Refining of the regulatory environment - creation of new standards
H – General Public	<p>End users who benefit from the project outcomes, civil society.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge acquisition

3.4 REFLOW Capacity Building Framework

Figure 3 below describes the overall approach to Capacity Building as implemented within REFLOW. The subsections detail each objective and approach and expected outcomes within the framework.

Figure 3: REFLOW Capacity Building Framework

3.4.1 Establishment and management of a Community of Practice around Circular cities.

Objective

- Bring together active individuals and organisations focusing on enabling the development of circular and regenerative cities.
- The community of practice will share knowledge, tools, methodologies and feedback on the current state of implementation of circular cities at practice level.

Approach

The community of practice provides insights on the skills, competences, knowledge and tools necessary to enable circular cities, while on the other hand, it is the main recipient of the new knowledge and tools developed within the reflow project.

REFLOW will:

- Facilitate inclusive exchange between member of the consortium as well as their ecosystems (Policymakers, SMEs, NGOs, and educational institutions).
- Engage in collaboration with external stakeholders (existing city alliances, sister projects) for cooperating on capacity building efforts and achieving greater synergies

These will ensure that information is shared on needs, knowledge and best practice. The detailed community of practice development framework and its implementation is described in deliverable 6.2.

Outcome

A community of practice around circular cities is established.

3.4.2 Competence Framework Development

Objective

- Organize competences into distinctive sets supporting the development of circular cities.
- Identify the knowledge, skills and competences sets for each area.

Approach

Organize competences sets into specific spheres based on literature. Some competences are related to generic sustainability areas (such as system thinking, or future thinking competences); others are technical and related to specific tasks to be performed within specific professions. Specific interpersonal competences are also needed to support the acquisition of other competences.

The approach integrates these interconnected competence sets into a comprehensive competence framework.

Outcome

A competence framework providing a set of competences and associated knowledge and skills to support the acceleration of circular economy in cities is developed and described.

3.4.3 Skills gap assessment**Objectives**

- Assess skills and competences at local level to enable the development of circular cities.
- Identify existing skills and competences supporting the current implementation of circular cities
- Analyse the skills gap between skills needs and existing skills to frame the Capacity building needs for the project.

Approach

Development of a multi-stakeholder survey addressing necessary skills and competences supporting the development of circular cities. The skills are framed and defined according to the target groups of the project.

Outcome

Skillsets and skills gap are identified and recommendations on Capacity building Resources pathways are developed.

3.4.4 Development of a Capacity Building Resource Portfolio**Objective**

Respond to the identified skills gap by developing a set of complementary resources that can support target groups in their activities.

Approach

Given the diversity of target groups, the resource portfolio will take a multi-stakeholder approach. Resources can be organized as entry level points (general knowledge for all) or be specifically developed for certain target groups (ie: businesses, policy makers, academia) based on their needs (advanced knowledge, practical tools or methodologies..)

Resources are organized with a key target group in mind.

Resources are organized based on the level on learning objectives required: Inspire, Inform, Connect, Equip, following the Reflow Capacity Building Pathway (detailed in section 4.3).

Outcome

A portfolio of resources integrating various learning approaches and learning objectives for all target groups is designed and ready to be implemented.

3.4.5 Capacity Building implementation**Objective**

Develop, share and disseminate the diverse capacity resources among the key target groups.

Approach

Resources are developed in a timely sequence. As the project evolves and additional needs emerge, it is safe to leave room for iteration of existing tools and development of new resources. The implementation sequence is described below (Section 4).

Outcome

A set of capacity building resources are developed and used by target groups of the project.

3.4.6 Monitoring**Objectives**

- Validate the relevance of the capacity building tools
- Monitor the progress in reducing the skills gap among target groups

Approach

Development of monitoring procedures related to resources developed

Outcome

A validated capacity building framework with well-functioning resources meeting the needs of the target groups of the project.

4. Implementation of the REFLOW Capacity Building Framework

This chapter describes the different activities to be performed in the project to support the implementation of the Capacity Building framework, starting from the development of a competence framework (section 4.1), through its use in a skills gap assessment (section 4.2), before framing the possible Capacity Building resources portfolio to be developed (section 4.3) throughout the project. The implementation phase and its respective monitoring (section 4.4) are detailed in subsequent deliverables D6.2, D6.3, D6.4, and D6.5.

4.1 REFLOW Competence Framework

4.1.1 Competence categorization

Accelerating the transition to circular and regenerative cities relies on a different set of skills, competences and approaches.

These competences can be drawn from generic skills sets associated to *sustainability competences* such as systems thinking, value thinking or futures thinking competences (Wiek et al. 2011, Wiek et al, 2015), in combination with *contextual competences* directly connected to the phenomenon of circular and regenerative cities, and *interpersonal competences*, which create the necessary conditions to develop and strengthen other competences.

Systems Thinking Competences

Ability to analyse sustainability problems and solutions cutting across different domains and scales; considering agents, cause-effect structures, cascading effects, inertia, feedback loops, etc.

- How actions, activities, and behaviours influence negative or positive outcomes;
- How actors' motives, needs, assumptions, and mandates influence actions, activities, and behaviour;
- What role technology and infrastructure play in problems and solutions;
- What effective intervention points are;
- What dynamics, cascading effects, and delays occur in problems and solutions

Values Thinking Competences

Ability to collectively map, specify, apply, reconcile, and negotiate sustainability values, principles, goals, and targets

- What sustainability principles and goals exist and how they are being justified;
- How justice norms vary across and within cultures and times;
- How integrity norms can guide goal setting
- What are the significant risks for the different stakeholders;
- How to specify and apply sustainability principles and goals

Futures Thinking Competences

Ability to anticipate how sustainability problems and solutions might evolve over time, considering alternative development pathways for current systems and crafting coherent and plausible pictures of the future

- What futures are plausible (scenarios);
- What future is most likely (forecast);
- What futures are desirable (visions);
- What futures are sustainable (visions based on sustainability principles);
- What significant future impacts could result from actions or technologies (e.g., shocks);
- What future coming generations might desire;
- How to discern which time scales are relevant to problems and solutions.

Strategic Thinking Competences

Ability to design and implement transformational (systemic) intervention and transition strategies toward sustainability

- What strategies for positive change exist in different cultures and times;
- How to apply theories of change;
- How to overcome barriers and utilize assets;
- How to create effective sequences of actions;
- How to coordinate actions among allies.

Technical level competence

- Level 1: Technical level 1 sets out the general knowledge, skills and competences needed to develop circular and regenerative cities
- Level 2: At this level, the requisite skill sets are focused and tailored to particular roles of target groups

Interpersonal Competences

Ability to work in teams, and understand, embrace, and facilitate diversity among cultures and social groups. Interpersonal competence is a basic ingredient in each of the other competences.

Figure 4: REFLOW Competence Framework

4.1.2 Learning outcomes for each competence

System thinking Competences – learning outcomes

Systems-thinking competence means that learners have the ability to understand the intermediate and root causes of complex sustainability problems, including how causes and effects relate to each other directly and indirectly; the actions, needs, motives, intentions, and mandates of key players in the problem constellation, the dynamics, cascading effects, feedback loops, and inertia occur in the constellation.

KNOWLEDGE:
Has knowledge of important sustainability aspects in urban development , such as population, economy and growth, resources, climate, environment and health as well as biodiversity
Has knowledge of the social, environmental and economic impacts of urban development .
Has understanding of cities and their design as complex systems in which different contexts, structures and changes mutually affect each other
Has thorough knowledge and understanding of the framework conditions and challenges of organisations in relation to the development and design of circular cities,
Is able to understand and, on a scientific basis, reflect on the development of circular cities at the organisational level , as well as to identify relevant problems in this context
Has thorough knowledge and understanding of different societal interests and roles of actors in relation to sustainable urban development as well as the possibilities and challenges characterizing the interplay between different actors
Has knowledge of theories of science and research methods relevant to the analysis of the roles of organisations in sustainable urban development.
Has knowledge of the interaction of the various actors and aspects of sustainability in an urban context
Has knowledge of discourses, institutions and actors as tools of analysis in relation to decision-making processes
SKILLS:
Can carry out investigations of sustainability aspects in an urban context in which the methodological approach takes into account the complex relations of cities
Can identify, analyse and assess relevant problems and impacts related to sustainability
Can understand, apply and critically reflect on relevant quantitative as well as qualitative economic, social, environmental and/or technical methods of analysis and identify the interests connected to these
Can independently collect relevant data in relation to the challenges and problems of the project, and assess the quality and reliability of this data
Can structure and manage the complex combination of specific challenges related to sustainable urban development at the organisational level in his/her work
Can understand different types of organisations; map important stakeholders and initiate a relevant dialogue with these
Can identify, analyse and assess project-related problems and impacts related to sustainability in a societal perspective, including understand the interplay between the local, regional and national levels
COMPETENCES:

Can participate /manage **interdisciplinary cooperation** in relation to economic, social and environmental assessment at city level

Values thinking competences – learning outcomes

Values thinking competences are normative. They include understanding concepts of justice, equity, social-ecological integrity, and ethics. They also include a thorough understanding of how these concepts vary across and within cultures, and how integrating these concepts contributes to solving sustainability problems. Using methods such as visioning, multi-criteria assessment, and risk assessment, learners are able to collaborate with stakeholders to specify, negotiate, and apply sustainability values, principles, objectives, and goals. This enables learners to assess the (un-) sustainability of current and future states of social-ecological systems, and to create and craft sustainability visions for these systems.

KNOWLEDGE:

Has a thorough understanding of the concepts of **justice, equity, social-ecological integrity, and ethics**

Has a thorough understanding of how these concepts vary **across and within cultures**, and how integrating these concepts contributes to solving sustainability problems.

SKILLS

Can use methods such as **visioning, multi-criteria assessment, and risk assessment**

COMPETENCES

Ability to collaborate with stakeholders to **specify, negotiate, and apply sustainability values**, principles, objectives, and goals.

Future thinking competences – learning outcomes

KNOWLEDGE:

Has understanding of the **concepts of sustainability and circular economy** in a global context

Has knowledge of different **models for the design and development of cities with a sustainability and circularity approach** and the impacts of these models

Is familiar with different theories of **how the future emerges, be it determined, accidental, or intentional**

Has a thorough understanding of the different types of futures, i.e., **possible futures** (based on notions of plausibility), probable futures (those determined “likely” to occur), and **desirable futures** (value-laden; based on sustainability principles).

Has thorough knowledge of important **side effects** of the most common strategies for the promotion of consideration of sustainability in urban development

SKILLS:

Can **reflect critically on the relations between growth, innovation and sustainability** in the context of city development

Has the ability to **discern which time scales** are relevant to a problem and its possible solutions.

COMPETENCES:

Has an understanding of the corresponding ways to build these different futures using methods like **scenario construction, forecasting and back casting, and sustainability visioning**.

Technical competences – learning outcomes

The competences can be summarized as the ability to collaboratively design and implement interventions and governance strategies with the sophistication necessary to address sustainability challenges. In this set of competences, the knowledge and skills that comprise the other competencies are translated into action that creates change. Learners, in having these competencies are familiar with concepts and methods for strategy building in real-world situations. They understand intentionality, systemic inertia, path dependencies. They know about the viability, feasibility, efficiency, and efficacy of systemic interventions, and the potential of those interventions to produce unintended consequences. They are able to use methods for designing, testing, implementing, evaluating, and adapting policies, programs, and action plans in collaboration with different societal actors. They must be able to accommodate varying perspectives and acts despite in-conclusive or incomplete evidence.

KNOWLEDGE:
Has knowledge of project-related quantitative and qualitative economic, sociological, environmental and/or technical methods of analysis
Has thorough knowledge of selected types of tools and systems for the promotion of sustainability at city and organizational level
Has knowledge of planning processes related to sustainable urban development, including the influence of political, economic and other interests in relation to power
Has knowledge of political approaches which influence sustainability in urban development
Has knowledge of governance models in relation to multi-stakeholders decision-making processes
Has knowledge of methods and experiences in relation to the social development and conditions of life of the city
Has knowledge of economic impact assessment in the public and private sectors; social and environmental impact assessment, as well as the interaction between assessment, implementation and public regulation
Has knowledge of innovative business models and their significance for sustainability
Has knowledge of technological approaches to the promotion of sustainable innovation
SKILLS:
Can analyse and assess selected tools and approaches to embedding the sustainability efforts into the multiple layers of a city, from mapping and documentation to securing continuous improvements through motivation, participation, etc.
Can use the selected tools and approaches as the basis for developing proposals for sustainability-related improvements
Can, by the use of various tools, assess the effects of initiatives seen in relation to sustainable urban development.
Can analyse and critically reflect on policies, strategies and plans for urban development in terms of their impacts and potentials for urban development

Can understand, apply and critically reflect on relevant quantitative as well as qualitative economic, sociological, environmental and/or technical methods of analysis and identify the interests connected to these
Can independently collect data in relation to relevant societal problems and assess the quality and reliability of this data
Can assess and combine different approaches to promoting sustainability and circular economy in an urban context
Can critically analyse policies , strategies and models for sustainable urban development in a concrete context
COMPETENCES:
Can reflect critically on the selection of tools and approaches, including critically assess results and conclusions
Can understand and reflect on theory, assessment methods and analytical tools within the relevant fields
Can continually adjust and adapt different tools and systems to the present challenges of a city
Can combine and use relevant theories, understandings, methods and analyses in such a way that these form a synthesis aimed at the formulation of concrete strategies and plans for the work of the city with sustainable solutions
Can independently assess economic, social and environmental impacts in relation to sustainable urban development

Interpersonal competences – learning outcomes

Interpersonal competence is a basic ingredient in each of the other competencies.

KNOWLEDGE:
Has a thorough understanding of the role of individuals in the transition to circular cities
SKILLS:
Has the ability to reflect critically on the use of the concepts and methods of analysis presented
Is able to, independently, develop and introduce new concepts and methods of analysis in relation to problems relevant to his/her own professional competence
Can communicate knowledge of policies, planning and governance to specialists as well as non-specialists.
Can communicate the result of projects to a selected target audience
Can independently initiate and participate in interdisciplinary planning tasks and cooperation at the organisational level
Can analyse and understand the potentials and challenges in the development of cooperation relations, including public-private partnerships, networks, etc.
COMPETENCES:
Can independently initiate and participate in interdisciplinary planning tasks and cooperation across social levels, nationalities and cultures
Is able to develop professionally on a continuous basis through the acquisition of new knowledge of policy, planning and governance.

Can independently assume responsibility for his/her own professional development and specialization

4.2 Skills gap assessment

4.2.1 Objective of the assessment

Supporting, developing, and building capacity around circular economy opportunities is key to shifting systems. City governments can work with businesses, the community, and individuals to build capacity.

Initiatives to build individual, community, and business capacity to help drive circular economy activities include: stimulating skill development, running capacity-building online and face to face workshops, developing guides and toolkits, supporting physical community innovation and repair hubs, developing tailored capacity building programmes for local businesses, entrepreneurs and training centres...

In order to tailor the training resources to the needs of active stakeholders at city level, it is necessary to first identify and assess the skills and competences needed for each stakeholder and second, prioritize the skills that should be developed further based on existing levels of competence. Finally, it is also important to grasp how individuals generally want to learn.

4.2.2 Methodology

In order to gain insights on the type of competences and skills that could be further developed within the project, an online questionnaire was developed and distributed to the members of the consortium representing pilot cities and the associated partners providing supporting roles at EU level.

The questionnaire was organised in several sections described below.

Section 1. Tell us about yourself

The objective of this section is to be able to frame the nature of the respondents

- *type of occupation (city representative, NGO, SME, etc.)*
- *experience in relation to circular economy*
- *Vision and challenges related to circular economy*

Section 2. Competence self-assessment:

This section asks respondents to evaluate the importance of a different set of skills according to their occupation.

Knowledge, Skills and competences propositions were organised into 5 categories, following an adapted version of Wiek 2011, a reference framework on key competencies on sustainability.

- *Systems thinking competences*
- *Values thinking competences (normative)*
- *Future thinking competences (anticipatory)*

- *Technical competences (strategic)*
- *Interpersonal competences*

For each category, respondents were asked to evaluate the importance of the proposition on a 5 point likert type scale.

Proposition were derived from an overview of existing curriculum and trainings related to sustainable and circular cities, (for instance, a technical competence was formulated as: "Can independently assess economic, social and environmental impacts in relation to sustainable urban development").

Section 3. Your learning routines

This section asked respondents to define further their learning habits

- Form of training (workshop, lecture, etc.)
- Learning medium: computer-based, physical)
- Length of training

Section 4. Your view on capacity building resources

Respondents were asked to evaluate the importance of a set of learning resources that could be developed further in the framework of the Project. Open ended questions completed the evaluation to receive additional suggestions on possible resource needs.

The questionnaire was first developed as a paper version and distributed/tested among a selection of consortium/ partners to confirm the relevance, clarity, flow and phrasing of the questions. Following adaptation (wording, length) an online version of the questionnaire was developed using webropol, a survey and reporting tool (www.webropol.fi).

The questionnaire was distributed online through the Reflow mailing list between January and February 2020. In parallel, online interviews were held between January and February 2020 with City pilots representatives to discuss further needs associated to capacity building.

Results and recommendations are described in the next section.

4.2.3 Results of the assessment

The following subsections detail the key learnings extracted from the assessment.

4.2.3.1 Function/ roles of respondents in circular economy

Learnings

- The profile of respondents is varied and relates to the different stakeholders involved in circular city transition.
- City officers (10%), NGOs (24%), Consultants, Businesses/entrepreneurs, Makerspaces (14%), Academia (14%), citizens (5%)
- Other categories include cultural sector, technological providers, independent researchers.

Figure 5: Profile of respondents

4.2.3.2 Vision of circular economy in the context of the pilot city

Learnings

- There is no single vision for the project and the way circular economy is perceived among respondents.
- Rather, the vision described by individual respondents is multi-faceted.
- Vision of CE is either holistic, close to official definitions (EMF) or then takes a specific lens:
 - *Resource-centred*: focus on materials and flows within the city
 - *Technology-centred*: focus on the tech and data solutions
 - *Governance-centred*: focus on the mode of organising the transition
 - *Business-centred*: focus on companies' role and involvement
 - *Challenge-centred*: focus on specific local city issues and their associated strategies
 - *Behaviour-centred*: focus on the change of mind-sets, involvement of citizens.

Insights: quotes from respondents

Holistic visions

- Circular economy as a way to develop solutions to recirculate resource flows, while engaging citizens and other stakeholders to co-create meaningful solutions
- Circular economy as an economic system in which we move from a linear process of extraction - transformation - consumption - waste, into a circular one in which a higher utility and value is extracted from resources. This involves higher recovering, regenerating, reusing and recycling of materials and products, through generating new goods, new uses and engaging new users. This transition would involve cities to shift from consuming and wasting into producing and transforming.
- Circular economy as a re-ideation of our local economy and city, that implies change from everything and everybody involved or connected in this city.
- Circular economy as a vision achievable when all the actors involved find their place and the environment in which they aim to do so, is enabling.
- Circular Economy as a set of complementary elements that form a concept.
- It is a vision of a sustainable and viable ecosystem (from socio-economical-environmental perspectives), that is self-sustainable, adapts constantly and always involves society as a whole.

Resource centred visions

- Creating a city where as little waste as possible is generated, and where waste is regarded as a resource.
- An economic and ecological system aimed at eliminating waste
- Increasing the circularity of material flows
- Material reused, upcycled, recycled

Challenge-centred visions

- Reduction of the amounts of discarded and destroyed/incinerated textiles
- We have to use textile products much longer and have to recycle discarded textiles into secondary fibres which can be used again in high added value textile products
- Reusing waste water for private households or businesses.
- Introduce circularity in event and support the actors of the Circular Economy.

- Circular Economy in energy is related to the flow of the energy in the city, energy entering the city through providers, how this energy is consumed and what remains (pollution, losses, etc...)

Business-centred visions

- An opportunity for business creation, new jobs

Governance-centred visions

- CE is a process that needs both top-down and bottom-up approaches.
- CE is a new way of being a food consumer, promoter, producers and seller.
- The latter requires a new mind-set for citizenship, that represents the core of the transition. I think that the main effort of the project must focus on citizen engagement and on the implementation phase.

Technology-centred visions

- We are challenging Circular Economy with Digital Tools and Knowledge in order to maximize impact of our projects.
- The municipality and city want to be innovative in being circular alongside a growing population, a growing consumption and a shift in the welfare-system, where the citizens and companies play a bigger part by self-help and being resilient to preventing the challenges of tomorrow. Also, by combining use of technology, design-methods and including stakeholders in the challenge, it is our belief, that new business-models will show the way forward, when making plastic circular and reducing the need of plastic.

Behaviour-centred visions

- CE is based on a deep transformation of habits and behaviour, but with a clear environmental goal.
- CE is purposive, but is not just about sustainability environmentally, the socio-economic components are fundamental for this transition to happen. This happens in mind set and cultural rituals: from the way we consume, purchase and dispose, all the way to how we see and value resources present or even abundant around us.
- CE is important in order to increase citizens' quality of life

4.3.2.3 Key activities of respondents related to circular economy

Learnings

The respondents illustrate a variety of activities related to the management of a circular transition.

Insights: illustration of activities

City level

- Involving and connecting a wide range of local stakeholders.
- Developing new prototypes and consequently enabling scaling and replication in other cities
- Executing citizens' engagement and capacity building activities.
- Supervising energy consumption at city level.
- Electrical energy acquisition for the public buildings

Consultancy

- Training and consultancy associated with CE (business model innovation, research and knowledge production)
- Advising companies and institutions on circular and sustainable textiles.
- Knowledge transfer between cities.
- Research, advisory, and consultancy to cities on how to move to circularity, implement circular strategies and develop and use key technologies in their environment.
- Development of training and incubation program

Business

- Company dedicated to the production of cellulose out of textile waste
- Designing and implementing decentralised technology to enable the value flows of material.

NGO

- Engaging with other CE projects and initiatives to facilitate knowledge exchange.
- Policy-making and collaborative governance support: helping the pilot cities in further developing or creating systemic policies for CE, able to achieve positive impacts across different sectors and 'horizontal domains' such as citizens' engagement, governance, and capacity-building.
- Support and develop a local and circular production

Researcher and educational institutes

- Research and writing
- Solution for improving energy efficiency and for energy production from renewable sources.
- Training consumer for increasing awareness in energy consumption.
- City talks with experts and makers around sustainable architecture, fashion and design.

Citizens

- Invest in materials/products/services that try to take steps towards a circular and more sustainable society.

4.3.2.4 Experience of respondents

Learnings

- 62% of respondents have been working on the field for more than 2 years
- 38% of respondents have been for working on the field for a year or less.

Figure 6: Years of experience of respondents

4.3.2.5 Needs and challenges faced in daily activities in relation to circular cities

Learnings

FROM THEORY TO IMPLEMENTATION

- Poor capacity to make actionable strategies that can translate into concrete roadmaps;
- Difficulty in finding practical implementations of CE strategies
- Complexity in operationalization of solutions
- Challenge in translating topics into practice

CULTURAL CHALLENGE

- Shifting of mind sets
- Behavioural issues

CITIZENS ENGAGEMENT

- Concrete actions that can be taken by everyone to promote CE. Many people like the idea of CE but don't know where to start in their everyday choices, both in their jobs as well as in their private life.
- Lack of awareness by citizens
- Make the topic tangible and comprehensible for all target groups

BUSINESS CHALLENGE

- The challenge is to help local actors to be competitive.
- Getting businesses involved
- Scaling up issues for businesses
- Lack of business advisor Skills

GOVERNANCE CHALLENGES

- Alignment with different stakeholders

TECHNOLOGICAL CHALLENGES

- Poor Digital Culture of the designers and makers
- The lack of data alliance between private and public parties
- Lack of material science expertise

THEORETICAL CHALLENGES

- Lack of common understanding
- Complexity

4.3.2.6 Motivation to develop new competences with regards to current role

Learnings

- 81% of respondents intend to develop new competences to improve their current role.
- Other motivations include:
 - Personal interest
 - The will to drive technology to crucial human challenges
 - Explore possibilities that we haven't even yet imagined

Figure 7: Motivation to acquire new competences

4.3.2.7 Skills and competences assessment

System thinking skills

Learnings

3 most important identified skills

- **KNOWLEDGE:** knowledge of different roles of actors and understanding the interplay between different actors.
- **SKILLS:** map important stakeholders and initiate dialogue with them
- **COMPETENCE:** manage interdisciplinary cooperation in relation to economic, social and environmental assessment at city level

Recommendation

- Stakeholder management as part of upcoming toolkit

	Low importance	Moderately important	Important	Very important	No answer	Average	Median
Have knowledge of important sustainability aspects in urban development, such as population, economy and growth, resources, climate, environment and health as well as biodiversity	0%	19.05%	47.62%	28.57%	4.76%	3.19	3
Have knowledge of the social, environmental and economic impacts of urban development.	4.76%	0%	38.1%	52.38%	4.76%	3.52	4
Have understanding of cities and their design as complex systems in which different contexts, structures and changes mutually affect each other.	4.76%	28.57%	14.29%	47.62%	4.76%	3.19	4
Have thorough knowledge and understanding of different societal interests and roles of actors in relation to sustainable urban development as well as the possibilities and challenges characterizing the interplay between different actors.	4.76%	9.52%	19.05%	52.38%	14.29%	3.62	4
Can carry out investigations of sustainability aspects in an urban context in which the methodological approach takes into account the complex relations of cities	0%	30%	25%	30%	15%	3.3	3
Can identify, analyse and assess relevant problems and impacts related to sustainability	9.52%	14.29%	38.1%	33.33%	4.76%	3.1	3
Can understand, apply and critically reflect on relevant quantitative as well as qualitative economic, social, environmental and/or technical methods of analysis and identify the interests connected to these	0%	19.05%	33.33%	42.86%	4.76%	3.33	3
Can structure and manage the complex combination of specific challenges related to sustainable urban development at the organisational level in his/her work.	4.76%	14.29%	38.09%	28.57%	14.29%	3.33	3

Can understand different types of organisations (both institutional and bottom-up); map important stakeholders and initiate a relevant dialogue with these	0%	4.76%	14.29%	76.19%	4.76%	3.81	4
Can identify, analyse and assess project-related problems and impacts related to sustainability in a societal perspective, including understand the interplay between the local, regional and national levels.	4.76%	4.76%	42.86%	42.86%	4.76%	3.38	3
Can manage interdisciplinary cooperation in relation to economic, social and environmental assessment at city level	9.52%	0%	19.05%	66.67%	4.76%	3.57	4

Value-thinking skills

Learnings: most important identified skills

- **KNOWLEDGE:** understanding of how sustainability and circularity concepts vary across and within cultures
- **SKILLS:** use methods such as visioning, multi-criteria impact assessment, and risk assessment
- **COMPETENCE:** Have the ability to collaborate with stakeholders to specify, negotiate, and apply sustainability values, principles, objectives, and goals.

Recommendation:

- Stakeholder management as part of upcoming toolkit

	Low importance	Moderately important	Important	Very important	No answer	Average	Median
Have a thorough understanding of the concepts of justice, equity, social-ecological integrity, and ethics	19.05%	28.57%	33.33%	14.29%	4.76%	2.57	3
Have a thorough understanding of how these concepts vary across and within cultures, and how integrating these concepts contributes to solving sustainability problems.	9.52%	14.29%	23.81%	42.86%	9.52%	3.29	4
Can use methods such as visioning, multi-criteria assessment, and risk assessment	9.52%	28.57%	19.05%	38.1%	4.76%	3	3
Have the ability to collaborate with stakeholders to specify, negotiate, and apply sustainability values, principles, objectives, and goals.	0%	0%	33.33%	61.91%	4.76%	3.71	4

Future thinking skills

Learnings: most important identified skills

KNOWLEDGE:

- Have understanding of the concepts of sustainability and circular economy in a local and global context
- Knowledge of different models for the development and design of cities with a sustainability and circularity approach and the impacts of these models

Recommendation:

- Development of Circular economy entry-level learning resources.
- Focus on general concept, and different building blocks: governance, tech, business models, etc.

	Low importance	Moderately important	Important	Very important	No answer	Average	Median
Have an understanding of the concepts of sustainability and circular economy in a local and global context	0%	0%	33.33%	57.14%	9.53%	3.76	4
Have knowledge of different models for the development and design of cities with a sustainability and circularity approach and the impacts of these models	0%	20%	25%	50%	5%	3.4	4
Have a thorough understanding of the different types of futures, i.e., possible futures (based on notions of plausibility), probable futures (those determined "likely" to occur), and desirable futures (value-laden; based on sustainability principles).	4.76%	9.53%	71.43%	4.76%	9.52%	3.05	3
Have thorough knowledge of important side effects of the most common strategies for the promotion of consideration of sustainability in urban development	0%	4.76%	61.91%	23.81%	9.52%	3.38	3
Can reflect critically on the relations between growth, innovation and sustainability in the context of city development	0%	14.29%	57.14%	23.81%	4.76%	3.19	3
Have the ability to discern which time scales are relevant to a problem and its possible solutions.	0%	14.29%	57.14%	23.81%	4.76%	3.19	3
Have an understanding of the corresponding ways to build these different futures using methods like scenario construction, forecasting and back casting, and sustainability visioning.	4.76%	28.57%	38.09%	14.29%	14.29%	3.05	3

Strategic and technical skills

Learnings: Most important identified skills

KNOWLEDGE:

- On new technological approaches to the promotion of sustainable innovation

SKILLS:

- Assess and combine different approaches to promoting sustainability and circular economy in an urban context
- Combine and use relevant theories, understandings, methods and analyses in such a way that these form a synthesis aimed at the formulation of concrete strategies and plans for the work of the city with sustainable solutions

COMPETENCES:

- Assess economic, social and environmental impacts in relation to sustainable urban development

Recommendations:

- Development of learning resources on the role of new tech
- Multi-level perspective resources.
- Actionable toolkits based on a variety of methods and tools
- Learning resources on social impact assessment

	Low importance	Moderately important	Important	Very important	No answer	Average	Median
Have knowledge of project-related quantitative and qualitative economic, sociological, environmental and/or technical methods of analysis	4.76%	33.33%	28.57%	23.81%	9.53%	3	3
Have thorough knowledge of selected types of tools and systems for the promotion of sustainability at city and organizational level	4.76%	23.81%	42.86%	23.81%	4.76%	3	3
Have knowledge of planning processes related to sustainable urban development, including the influence of political, economic and other interests in relation to power	9.53%	33.33%	38.1%	9.52%	9.52%	2.76	3
Have knowledge of political approaches which influence sustainability in urban development	4.76%	23.81%	38.1%	23.81%	9.52%	3.1	3
Have knowledge of governance models in relation to multi-stakeholders decision-making processes	4.76%	19.05%	42.86%	28.57%	4.76%	3.1	3
Have knowledge of methods of experimentations and prototyping in relation to the social development and conditions of life of the city	4.76%	23.81%	28.57%	33.33%	9.53%	3.19	3
Have knowledge of economic impact assessment in the public and private sectors; social and environmental impact assessment, as well as the interaction between assessment, implementation and public regulation	4.76%	33.33%	38.1%	14.29%	9.52%	2.9	3
Have knowledge of innovative business models and their significance for sustainability	4.76%	19.05%	28.57%	42.86%	4.76%	3.24	3
Have knowledge of new technological approaches to the promotion of sustainable innovation	0%	19.05%	19.05%	52.38%	9.52%	3.52	4
Can analyse and assess selected tools and approaches to embedding the sustainability efforts into the multiple layers of a city, from	9.52%	28.57%	28.57%	19.05%	14.29%	3	3

mapping and documentation to securing continuous improvements through motivation, participation, etc.							
Can use the selected tools and approaches as the basis for developing proposals for sustainability-related improvements	10%	40%	35%	10%	5%	2.6	2.5
Can, by the use of various tools, assess the effects of initiatives seen in relation to sustainable urban development.	10%	25%	35%	15%	15%	3	3
Can analyse and critically reflect on policies, strategies and plans for urban development in terms of their impacts and potentials for urban development	9.53%	33.33%	19.05%	28.57%	9.52%	2.95	3
Can understand, apply and critically reflect on relevant quantitative as well as qualitative economic, sociological, environmental and/or technical methods of analysis and identify the interests connected to these	0%	28.57%	38.09%	19.05%	14.29%	3.19	3
Can independently collect data in relation to relevant societal problems and assess the quality and reliability of this data	28.57%	4.76%	28.57%	19.05%	19.05%	2.95	3
Can assess and combine different approaches to promoting sustainability and circular economy in an urban context	4.76%	14.28%	42.86%	23.81%	14.29%	3.29	3
Can understand and reflect on theory, assessment methods and analytical tools within the relevant fields.	4.76%	28.57%	38.09%	14.29%	14.29%	3.05	3
Can continually adjust and adapt different tools and systems to the present challenges of a city	0%	28.57%	23.81%	38.1%	9.52%	3.29	3
Can combine and use relevant theories, understandings, methods and analyses in such a way that these form a synthesis aimed at the	0%	25%	35%	25%	15%	3.3	3

formulation of concrete strategies and plans for the work of the city with sustainable solutions							
Can independently assess economic, social and environmental impacts in relation to sustainable urban development	0%	28.57%	42.86%	14.28%	14.29%	3.14	3

Interpersonal skills

Learnings: most important identified skills

- **KNOWLEDGE:** understand the potentials and challenges in the development of cooperation relations, including public-private partnerships, networks, etc.
- **SKILLS:** communicate the result of projects to a selected target audience
- **COMPETENCES:** initiate and participate in interdisciplinary planning tasks and cooperation across social levels, nationalities and cultures

Recommendations:

- “Development of a Communicating circularity” set of learning resources.
- Citizen engagement resources.
- Planning/action plan development/ cooperation resources.

	Low importance	Moderately important	Important	Very important	No answer	Average	Median
Have a thorough understanding of the role of individuals (citizens) in the transition to circular cities	9.53%	9.52%	23.81%	52.38%	4.76%	3.33	4
Ability to, independently, develop and introduce new concepts and methods of analysis in relation to problems relevant to his/her own professional competence	0%	23.81%	42.86%	28.57%	4.76%	3.14	3
Communicate knowledge of policies, planning and governance to specialists as well as non-specialists.	4.76%	33.33%	23.81%	28.57%	9.53%	3.05	3
Communicate the result of projects to a selected target audience	4.76%	0%	28.57%	61.91%	4.76%	3.62	4
Independently initiate and participate in interdisciplinary planning tasks and cooperation at multi-organisational level	0%	4.76%	38.1%	52.38%	4.76%	3.57	4
Analyse and understand the potentials and challenges in the development of cooperation relations, including public-private partnerships, networks, etc.	0%	0%	38.1%	57.14%	4.76%	3.67	4
Independently initiate and participate in interdisciplinary planning tasks and cooperation across social levels, nationalities and cultures	0%	15%	20%	60%	5%	3.55	4

4.3.2.8 Priorisation of skills sets

Learnings

- Technical competences are prioritised
- Future thinking and interpersonal competences come second and third respectively

Additional skills/competences not directly listed but mentioned

- Funding skills: raising money required for the initiatives
- Business model development
- Material science
- Monitoring: carbon footprint analysis

Figure 8: Prioritization of skills and competences

4.3.2.9 Learning methods

Type of medium

- 70% of respondents favour offline learning in the form of short, facilitated workshops
- 80% of respondents would enjoy short online learning either scheduled (45%) or self-paced (35%)

- Other suggestions include
 - Coaching mentoring through online sessions
 - Using a format called "distributed workshop" and crafted for lab-to-lab learning with local communities.
 - A combination of an online workshop and an offline workshop, happening simultaneously in multiple locations connected.

Figure 9: Preferred learning methods

Duration

- 50 percent of respondents are used to short learning nuggets
- Trainings lasting less than a day are also favoured by 45% of the respondents.

Figure 10: Preference regarding duration of training

Learning technology

- 90% of respondents are used to use computer for their learning routines
- 55% focus on physical learning environments

Figure 11: Learning technology

Recommendations for learning methods

A blended learning approach should be developed:

- Prioritise micro-learning approaches (short online content)
 - Development of generic online resources. Access to existing resources.
- Developing training content to be used in workshop format for 1/2 day to a day.
 - Slide deck of content to be used in workshop / seminars
 - Creation of specific toolkits designed to be self-usable in local context

4.3.2.10 Evaluation of learning resources propositions to be developed in the context of REFLOW

In order of importance, the learning resources should focus on:

- Short inspirational content (3.35)
- Practical Toolkits (3.2)
- How to guidance (average: (3.05)
- Webinars (3.1)
- Business case databases (2.95)
- Circular policy databases (2.62)
- E-course (2,45)

Figure 12: Evaluation of learning resources envisioned for REFLOW

	Low importance	Moderately important	Important	Very important	No answer	Total	Average	Median
Abstracts, executive summaries (articles, reports)	1	6	8	5	0	20	2.85	3
Inspirational short content (videos, best practices)	2	0	8	9	1	20	3.35	3.5
Collection of circular policies	3	6	8	4	0	20	2.62	3
Collection of circular business cases	2	3	9	6	0	20	2.95	3
How to guidance (handbooks)	2	3	8	6	1	20	3.05	3
Practical toolkits ready to be implemented	2	1	9	7	1	20	3.2	3
Short Webinars on specific topics	1	5	6	7	1	20	3.1	3
Extensive E-course on specific topics	3	10	4	1	2	20	2.45	2
Total	16	34	60	45	6	20	2.94	3

4.3 Organising Capacity Building Resources: REFLOW Capacity Building Resources Pathway

In order to classify capacity building resources, the following diagram - the *REFLOW Capacity Building Resources Pathway* - is presented below.

Figure 13: REFLOW Capacity Building Resources Pathway

The approach organizes resources in 4 different steps: Get Inspired, Get Informed, Get Connected, Get Equipped. Each step is detailed below.

4.3.1 Get Inspired

Beyond knowledge sharing on key circular economy concepts, capacity building can be strategically framed to inspire the target groups involved in circular economy related practices at city level. There, inspiration on “what can be done/what is being implemented” in existing practices can also support stakeholders in their transition initiatives. Successful examples of circular policies, circular business models can be highlighted to provide a set of inspirational practices to be replicated or adapted.

4.3.2 Get Informed

The transition to circular cities necessitates understanding of a variety of concepts. Framed in the general concept of sustainability, the circular economy body of knowledge is built upon specific schools of thought, principles and conditions that are delineating the project. As REFLOW focuses on a city context, there is a need on one hand to provide target groups a comprehensive set of information related

to the above mentioned concepts as well as to establish on the other hand how these concepts are bridged with urban development, city governance, citizens participation, etc.

4.3.3 Get Connected

The third step is framed within engagement strategies, which allow stakeholders not only to be passive recipients of knowledge but provide space for exchange of good practices. Following a peer-to-peer process, these resources are developed to build upon the constant learning being revealed throughout the project.

4.3.4 Get Equipped

Finally, as new knowledge is being integrated within the project, specific toolkits, handbooks and methodologies are published and ready to be used for target groups at city level. These resources are built to provide hands-on instructions, methods, and tools on how to concretely implement CE strategies at city level.

4.4 Capacity building tools: An initial portfolio of capacity building resources

A multitude of stakeholders are active in the circular economy field. This results in a large quantity of projects, resources, and tools that involve capacity building. The information on activities and organisations is scattered and thus only available to limited groups of people. This means resources are less effectively and efficiently used.

REFLOW therefore aims to become a European repository of capacity building resources relevant to circular economy in the context of cities.

Beyond the curation of existing knowledge developed prior to the project, the Capacity building approach of REFLOW aims to respond to the skills gap assessment by developing a set of additional resources tailored to the needs of the pilot cities.

The following tools constitute the initial core of the REFLOW capacity building framework. It is expected that additional tools will emerge as new needs emerge.

RESOURCE 1	
NAME OF THE RESOURCE	GLOSSARY OF TERMS
Overview	The glossary is developed to create a common understanding of key terms and definitions associated with the objectives of the project and the topic of interest
Intervention	GET INFORMED
Audience	
Primary Audience	all
Secondary Audience	all
Outcome	
Learning objectives	Understand the terms and concepts associated with circular and regenerative economy
Learning outcomes	Ability to comprehend, discuss and share understanding of main concepts related to circular and regenerative economy
Modalities	
Learning environment	Online database hosted on the REFLOW website
Resources	Sources from partners, publications of existing reports on CE and RE
Evaluation/assessment protocol	
Mode of assessment	Self-assessment

Evaluation of impact	Number of page visits on website
Faculty	Glossary written by project members
Content overview	30 key themes defined and explained.

RESOURCE 2	
NAME OF THE RESOURCE	Database of Circular Business models
Overview	Provide inspiring examples of business models fitting with circular and regenerative practices in urban context. Special focus on sectors/areas of pilot projects
Intervention	GET INSPIRED
Audience	
Primary Audience	Businesses
Secondary Audience	Academia, business support organisations, consultancies
Outcome	
Learning objectives	Discover the diversity of business models operating in circular and regenerative economy
Learning outcomes	Understand the value creation, delivery and capture mechanisms of circular business models
Modalities	
Learning environment	Online database hosted on reflow website
Resources	Sources from partners, publications of existing case studies
Evaluation/assessment protocol	
Mode of assessment	self-assessment
Evaluation of impact	number of page visits on website
Faculty	Business cases written by project members.
Content overview	Database of at least 50 cases. Classified according to the main focus of project (waste, textile, buildings, food...). Description of value creation, delivery and capture mechanisms. Description of societal impact. Cases geographically situated in pilot cities first.

RESOURCE 3	
NAME OF THE RESOURCE	Database of Regenerative and Circular policies
Overview	The database provides practical examples of policies shaping the development of regenerative cities
Intervention	GET INSPIRED
Audience	
Primary Audience	Policy makers
Secondary Audience	Academia
Outcome	
Learning objectives	Understand the diversity of policymaking tools available for cities to transition to a circular and regenerative city
Learning outcomes	Policymakers are able to design adapted policies for their cities to become circular
Modalities	
Learning environment	online database hosted on reflow website
Resources	sources from partners, publications of existing report, learnings from pilots
Evaluation/assessment protocol	
Mode of assessment	self-assessment
Evaluation of impact	number of pages visits on website
Faculty	content written by project members
Content overview	Content is classified based on a typology of policy instruments. At least 30 policies are detailed and illustrated with examples. Expected impact of policy is described

RESOURCE 4	
NAME OF THE RESOURCE	REFLOW Collaborative Governance toolkit
Overview	Describes the common set of toolkits and frameworks to be used in the design and planning phase of regenerative cities
Intervention	EQUIP
Audience	
Primary Audience	Policy makers at city level, businesses
Secondary Audience	citizens
Outcome	
Learning objectives	Know the diversity of supporting tools enabling the development of circular and regenerative cities
Learning outcomes	
Modalities	

Learning environment	Online document to be downloaded. Access to specific toolkits.
Resources	-Existing toolkits.
Evaluation/assessment protocol	
Mode of assessment	Self-assessment
Evaluation of impact	Number of downloads
Faculty	Partners involved in WP4
Content overview	Description of toolkit, practical illustrations.

RESOURCE 5

NAME OF THE RESOURCE	Reflow hand book
Overview	REFLOW handbook for circular and regenerative cities includes instructional resources to implement CE practices in design, innovation and digital fabrication processes
Intervention	EQUIP
Audience	
Primary Audience	Policy makers, businesses
Secondary Audience	citizens
Outcome	
Learning objectives	Get familiar with practical tools and methodologies to support local stakeholders on their transition path to circular cities
Learning outcomes	Target group knows how to use a collection of tools for innovative approaches to the 21st century urban planning in cities.
Modalities	
Learning environment	Online.
Resources	Interactive pdf, to be downloaded.
Evaluation/assessment protocol	
Mode of assessment	Self-assessment
Evaluation of impact	Number of downloads. Documentation on how the handbook is being used in pilot cities.
Faculty	WP5 partners and WP leaders
Content overview	Description of urban strategies in line with circular, regenerative practices.

RESOURCE 6

NAME OF THE RESOURCE	Reflow webinars
Overview	Short videos detailing illustrative practices taking place within the community of practice
Intervention	Inform

Audience	
Primary Audience	Policy makers, businesses
Secondary Audience	Citizens
Outcome	
Learning objectives	Provide practical insights on the “how to” transition to circular cities.
Learning outcomes	Improved understanding of key challenges, barriers, solutions to the implementation of CE practices at city level
Modalities	
Learning environment	Online
Resources	Videos translated and spread into multichannel
Evaluation/assessment protocol	
mode of assessment	Self-assessment
evaluation of impact	Number of downloads on website
Faculty	Curation by Reflow partners. Interview of key stakeholders.
Content overview	Theme based (i.e. textile, plastic). Challenge based (engaging citizens, implementing open governance, etc.) Approach based (the role of Key enabling technologies in the transition..)

RESOURCE 7

NAME OF THE RESOURCE	Reflow starter kit
Overview	Crash information kit on circular cities. A package of short videos, PowerPoint, to explain circular and regenerative cities, reflow operating system and outcomes.
Intervention	Inform
Audience	
Primary Audience	all
Secondary Audience	all
Outcome	
Learning objectives	Get a general understanding of circular economy as envisioned by Reflow
Learning outcomes	Ability to understand the main concept and vision of a Reflow circular economy
Modalities	
Learning environment	online
Resources	Videos, ppt. infographics.
Evaluation/assessment protocol	

mode of assessment	Self-assessment
evaluation of impact	Number of downloads.
Faculty	Partners providing expertise on concepts
Content overview	What is circular economy? What are circular cities? What is reflow? What is co-creation? How to start a reflow process?

RESOURCE 8

NAME OF THE RESOURCE	
Academic case studies	
Overview	Development of supporting material to teach CE at academic level. Cases describe a real situation with challenges and dilemma and offer an opportunity for students to apply theoretical content from their courses.
Audience	
Primary Audience	teachers
Secondary Audience	students in business schools
Outcome	
Learning objectives	Apply theoretical content in real case scenario involving CE practices.
Learning outcomes	
Modalities	
Learning environment	Offline. classroom
Resources	Text-based material. Additional material in the form of videos.
Evaluation/assessment protocol	
mode of assessment	Graded assessment based on written paper and or oral presentation
Evaluation of impact	Number of uses/downloads
Faculty	Written by research partners, based on practices from Pilots
Content overview	Different lenses can be associated to the challenges of circular city transition: citizen engagement, stakeholders engagement, business model innovation...

RESOURCE 9	
NAME OF THE RESOURCE	E-learning courses
Overview	Development of open online courses focusing on circular economy
Audience	
Primary Audience	All target groups of the project
Secondary Audience	-
Outcome	
Learning objectives	Understand the concepts, visions, methods, tools to implement CE in city and business contexts.
Learning outcomes	Applying CE practices in learner's professional position.
Modalities	
Learning environment	Online - learning platform
Resources	Text-based - videos, audio.
Evaluation/assessment protocol	
mode of assessment	Quiz
Evaluation of impact	Number of participants, completion
Faculty	Written by research partners, based on practices from Pilots
Content overview	Different lenses can be associated to the challenges of circular city transition: citizen engagement, stakeholders engagement, business model innovation...

4.5 REFLOW Capacity building implementation and monitoring

A detailed description of the development and the implementation of the REFLOW Capacity Building Resources is described in the following deliverables:

Name of Deliverable	Objective and description
D.6.2 Community of Practice	This report introduces the community of practice overarching strategy for the REFLOW project. The aim of this document is to lay the ground for the motivation of developing a CoP around circular cities, define the target groups, the recruitment strategy and the implementation actions leading to the management of the community.
D6.3 Capacity Building Toolkit	This deliverable introduces and describes the Capacity Building Resources developed within the REFLOW project. It highlights a set of resources organised according to a Capacity Building Pathway: Get inspired, Get informed, Get connected and Get Equipped. The Deliverable also introduces a toolkit to support city stakeholders in organising their own capacity building strategy to be implemented as part of their circular city strategy.
D6.4 Multi-Platform Digital Resources and Structured Learning Courses	This deliverable introduces and describes the various digital resources and educational artefacts developed in the framework of the REFLOW project, under the umbrella "REFLOW Academy". Its purpose is to provide a set of relevant capacity building material while reflecting as a whole on the different pathways one city and its ecosystem of actors can take to acquire the relevant skills and knowledge necessary for a successful transition.
D6.5 Collaborative Case Studies	This deliverable introduces and describes the various academic case studies developed for teaching purposes based on the circular practices of the REFLOW Pilot Cities.

5. Conclusions

The deliverable 6.1 REFLOW Capacity Building Framework aimed to introduce how the concept of Capacity Building is framed within the REFLOW project. Following an overview of definitions and concepts, it introduced a framework used to support Capacity Building activities of the project. The document acted as a supporting tool to frame and develop the remaining deliverables of Work Package 6 in which detailed resources and activities are described.

Replication to other Circular City projects

The developed framework was designed to be replicated in other projects in which Capacity Building activities are foreseen. By describing a competence framework detailing key knowledge, skills and competences foreseen in the transition to Circular Cities, laying out a process to identify skills gap and finally providing examples of Capacity Building Resources, the deliverable can act as a supporting document for further cities and regions to strategically design a Circular Capacity Building Programme. Readers are invited to access other deliverables in this work package to get a better understanding of the detailed resources developed within the project

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